

D3.3 Environmental and socio-economic labels

Project Title	JOINING ACTORS FOR LOCAL DEVELOPMENT OF NEW LARGE-SCALE REGIONAL ENERGY COMMUNITIES
Acronym	LIFE21-CET-ENERCOM-JALON
Grant Agreement	101076395
Coordinator	Universidad Politécnica de Madrid

Deliverable title	D3.3 Environmental and socio-economic labels	
Work package	WP3	
Lead partner	CALAT-UPM	
Type	R - Document	
Dissemination Level	PU	Public
Due Date	31 October 2023	
Version	1.0	

Disclaimer

The information in this document is provided as is and no guarantee or warranty is given that the information is fit for any particular purpose. The user thereof uses the information at its sole risk and liability.

The content of this report reflects only the authors' view. The European Commission is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains.

Statement of Originality

This deliverable contains original unpublished work except where clearly indicated otherwise. Acknowledgement of previously published material and of the work of others has been made through appropriate citation, quotation, or both.

Content

1. Context 4

2. Environmental label- “Near Zero Emission” 4

2.1 Baseline limits calculation 4

2.2 Definition of the different categories for the label 6

2.2.1 Households 6

 Definition of the equations to calculate the labels 11

2.2.2 Industries 11

 Definition of the equations to calculate the labels 12

2.2.3 Services 13

 Definition of the equations to calculate the labels 16

2.2.5 Municipalities 16

2.2.6 Ad-hoc calculation for Jalon participants 20

3. Socio-economic label: “Reverting depopulation” 21

3.1. Social indicators to evaluate the impact of the energy community 25

4. Future use of the labels 27

5. References 29

APPENDIX 31

1. Definition of the different categories for the label 31

2. Definition of the equations to calculate the labels 32

 Carbon footprint calculation for the electricity consumption 32

 Carbon footprint calculation for the thermal energy consumption 32

 Carbon footprint calculation for transport energy consumption 33

 Overall carbon footprint 34

1. Context

It is obvious that the promotion of renewable energy communities is a way of promoting at the same time the objectives of the Climate Change and the Clean Energy Transition Subprogram.

However, to significantly raise awareness about the synergies between investments in renewable energy, reduction in energy consumption, and major energy efficiency, aligning with the idea proposed in another EU project (AURORA-Green Deal call-101036418), this deliverable aims to establish a tangible framework for evaluating changes made toward these objectives within the JALON project. Our goal is to adapt and expand upon the 'citizens label' developed in the AURORA project, introducing the 'Near Zero Emission' label for households, municipalities, shops, businesses, companies, and associations. This will empower individuals to act responsibly based on their awareness of their energy-related impact on the climate and enable consumers to make more informed choices when purchasing from local establishments. Monitoring and quantification will be carried out in task 4.5.

On the other hand, the improvement of the rural areas quality of life is one of the cornerstone of our proposal and set the specific objective number 1, Calatayud county aims at generating using the energy community as a way of keeping alive the rural areas life. At the moment, there are no previous cases reported at the literature identifying in a quantitative way how an energy community providing an stable, secure and innovative energy framework for the county inhabitants can serve to get the expected social benefits for such inhabitants, i.e. renewable energies acceptance, increase of the economic activity, new investments for the county, etc. in reality neither we have studies on the supposed economic benefit that citizens have. Then, although it seems that the consequences of such friendlier environment, and even more within the current energy crisis, could generate positive social changes and improve the quality of life of these EU areas, JALON has a demonstrator large enough as to have reliable statistics and confident data as to set a task during the project to identify and quantify how the creation of the energy community is related with an improvement in the quality of life of Calatayud county and its inhabitants. This activity can be seen in the workplan, Task 3.4 through the Label 2 "Reverting-Depopulation-Process Village / County / Region" and will serve to quantify the socioeconomic impact and monitored and quantified in task 4.5.

2. Environmental label- "Near Zero Emission"

In this section, the environmental label, known as the 'Near-Zero Emissions' label, is defined. The environmental impact is measured based on the electrical energy consumption and the greenhouse gas emissions related to that consumption. We divided this label into three categories: citizens, services, and industries, explained in the following subsections.

2.1 Baseline limits calculation

The calculation procedure follows [1], where the objective of percentages of energy consumption reduction are established by the European Climate Pact [2]: 25% for domestic energy consumption, 25% for industry energy consumption and 14% for services energy consumption relative to the levels in 2015. Table 1 shows the different levels defined for the label and the percentages of consumption to reach the 'Near-Zero

Emissions' level (levels A [-25%, -50%] and A+ [<-50%]) for the energy consumption at the household level (left) and for industries and the services sector (at the centre and right side of the table, respectively). This breakdown and limits among different labels are not defined by an objective reason. There is nothing beyond our own decision to set a label C in the range [-5%, -10%] instead of [-5%, -15%]. However, it can be easily seen that grades have been defined to encourage behavioural changes. If we achieve awareness on moving to a better level with the small first behavioural changes on energy use most plausible will be further actions. On the contrary people can be incentivized if they find a high barrier to move from an average value with their first positive actions.

Table 1 Limits for the labelling system

Level	Residential	Industries	Services
A+	[< -50% average value]	[< -50% average value]	[< -50% average value]
A	[- 50% of the average value, - 25% average value]	[- 50% of the average value, - 25% average value]	[- 50% of the average value, - 14% average value]
B	[- 25% of the average value, - 10% average value]	[- 25% of the average value, - 10% average value]	[- 14% of the average value, - 8% average value]
C	[- 10% of the average value, - 5% average value]	[- 10% of the average value, - 5% average value]	[- 8% of the average value, - 5% average value]
D	[- 5% of the average value, average value]	[- 5% of the average value, average value]	[- 5% of the average value, average value]
E	[average value, +5% average value]	[average value, +5% average value]	[average value, +5% average value]
F	[+5% of the average value, 25% average value]	[+5% of the average value, 25% average value]	[+5% of the average value, 14% average value]
G	[> +25% average value]	[> +25% average value]	[> 14% average value]

The labelling system is based on the energy consumption and emissions reduction from 2015 to reach the 2030 goals. For the energy consumption data, Datadis [3] is the data source chosen for households, industries, services and municipalities. The labelling system is specific for each municipality due to the diversity between the different municipalities among the buildings and inhabitants. The calculation followed is explained below.

We downloaded the 2022 monthly electrical energy consumption data for each municipality for the three sectors mentioned above. We calculated the total amount of energy consumption for the year 2022. As we know the number of electricity supply contracts for each of the sectors, we calculated the average per household, industry and service for each municipality. The total amount of energy consumption per municipality is the sum of the households, industries and services in that municipality. The labelling system is based on the sum of the sector applying their percentages of reduction for reaching the 2030 goals (see Table 1). As we were not able to access the 2015 data, we calculated those values based on the energy consumption reduction between 2015 and 2022 found in Our World in Data [4] (6.21% and 0.9% for the EU and Spain, respectively). In this case, as the project is developed in Spain, we considered the reduction of 0.9% from 2015 values and the calculation with the data from 2022 to 2015 values is based in this percentage.

Based on these data the energy consumption label for each industry, service and household is calculated. These data are used for calculating the different “Near-Zero Emissions” household, industry, shop, association, town hall, school and municipality.

The label associated to the municipality is the sum of the industries, services and households of that municipality.

Although the label considers average figures for each sector, specific cases could be monitored and studied by applying the same methodology. However, we would need specific data from households, services, or industries from past years. This data could be collected from the participants in the JALON Project and evaluate their changes to get a JALON “Near-zero emission label” (see 2.2.6). But, since we aim to record collective changes, which sometimes result from indirect impacts of the JALON project, we also need to establish indicators that enable us to measure such changes as described below.

2.2 Definition of the different categories for the label

For all the cases, the calculation of the different labels is the same: a specific label for each municipality. The reason for this calculation is because not every village has the same number of industries, households or services. So, it is unfair to calculate an average for all the regions. This way, each village has an average in order to have an energy consumption average for each service in a municipality.

The following sections show the calculation and values for the energy consumption and emissions labels for the different sectors across Calatayud County. In APPENDIX, specifications for transport sector for citizens to reduce their emissions in their daily habits are explained for a more comprehensive energy behaviour reduction and awareness. In the framework of the AURORA project we have developed a label that will evaluate the personal changes that any citizen has by being involved in educational or transformative programs, such as in energy communities. This label is already implemented in an app, but it is designed in a more generalist way, while what we present in this deliverable are levels to be achieved for each house, industry or service in the region, based on their own historical data.

2.2.1 Households

Here, the ranges on household electricity consumption for each municipality are established in Table 2, where we can see the corresponding annual label for each house belonging to each municipality of the region. Table 3 shows the greenhouse gas emission corresponding to each household in each municipality. The emissions are calculated based on the emission factor of the national grid.

The yearly mean energy consumption per household is calculated as the total energy consumed by the domestic sector in a village divided by the number of existing energy supply contracts, both data obtained from Datadis. However, results show very low values compared to the average consumption values per dwelling in Spain (3776 kWh/year) as published by the JRC [5]. This may be due to the existence of many unoccupied dwellings that maintain a minimum electricity supply contract without annual consumption, and many other dwellings that may only be inhabited on holidays periods. When analysing a few examples, we decided to recalculate the energy consumption per household. We considered the municipal census for 2015 from the National Institute for Statistics (INE) [6] and, with an approximated mean of 2.5 people living in a household, we obtained the annual energy consumption for each dwelling in every village. These

values are closer to the average housing figures in Spain, which is why we have opted to keep these values, as shown in Table 2.

Therefore, the idea of evaluating JALON participants in a specific way is reinforced. If they give us their concrete data, we will be able to improve the evaluation of their energy performance (see 2.2.6).

Table 2. Energy consumption label for all households per municipality (kWh/year)

Municipality	A+	A	B	C	D	E	F	G
ABANTO	<1603	1603-2405	2405-2886	2886-3046	3046-3206	3206-3367	3367-4008	>4008
ALARBA	<1281	1281-1921	1921-2305	2305-2433	2433-2561	2561-2689	2689-3202	>3202
ALCONCHEL DE ARIZA	<2735	2735-4103	4103-4923	4923-5197	5197-5470	5470-5744	5744-6838	>6838
ALHAMA DE ARAGÓN	<1706	1706-2559	2559-3071	3071-3242	3242-3412	3412-3583	3583-4266	>4266
ANIÑÓN	<2071	2071-3107	3107-3728	3728-3935	3935-4142	4142-4350	4350-5178	>5178
ARÁNDIGA	<2025	2025-3037	3037-3644	3644-3847	3847-4049	4049-4252	4252-5061	>5061
ARIZA	<1818	1818-2727	2727-3272	3272-3454	3454-3635	3635-3817	3817-4544	>4544
ATECA	<1867	1867-2801	2801-3361	3361-3548	3548-3735	3735-3922	3922-4669	>4669
BELMONTE DE GRACIÁN	<1152	1152-1728	1728-2074	2074-2189	2189-2304	2304-2419	2419-2880	>2880
BERDEJO	<1074	1074-1611	1611-1933	1933-2040	2040-2147	2147-2255	2255-2684	>2684
BIJUESCA	<1844	1844-2766	2766-3319	3319-3503	3503-3688	3688-3872	3872-4609	>4609
BORDALBA	<1403	1403-2104	2104-2525	2525-2665	2665-2805	2805-2946	2946-3507	>3507
BUBIERCA	<1934	1934-2900	2900-3481	3481-3674	3674-3867	3867-4061	4061-4834	>4834
CABOLAFUENTE	<3830	3830-5745	5745-6895	6895-7278	7278-7661	7661-8044	8044-9576	>9576
CALATAYUD	<2149	2149-3224	3224-3869	3869-4083	4083-4298	4298-4513	4513-5373	>5373
CALMARZA	<2194	2194-3290	3290-3948	3948-4168	4168-4387	4387-4606	4606-5484	>5484
CAMPILLO DE ARAGÓN	<1204	1204-1806	1806-2167	2167-2288	2288-2408	2408-2528	2528-3010	>3010
CARENAS	<2370	2370-3555	3555-4266	4266-4503	4503-4740	4740-4977	4977-5925	>5925
CASTEJÓN DE ALARBA	<1309	1309-1963	1963-2355	2355-2486	2486-2617	2617-2748	2748-3271	>3271
CASTEJÓN DE LAS ARMAS	<1425	1425-2138	2138-2565	2565-2708	2708-2850	2850-2993	2993-3563	>3563
CERVERA DE LA CAÑADA	<1479	1479-2219	2219-2663	2663-2811	2811-2959	2959-3107	3107-3699	>3699
CETINA	<1700	1700-2550	2550-3059	3059-3229	3229-3399	3399-3569	3569-4249	>4249
CIMBALLA	<1831	1831-2747	2747-3297	3297-3480	3480-3663	3663-3846	3846-4579	>4579
CLARÉS DE RIBOTA	<1468	1468-2202	2202-2642	2642-2789	2789-2935	2935-3082	3082-3669	>3669
CODOS	<2425	2425-3637	3637-4364	4364-4607	4607-4849	4849-5091	5091-6061	>6061
CONTAMINA	<2444	2444-3666	3666-4399	4399-4643	4643-4888	4888-5132	5132-6109	>6109
EMBED DE ARIZA	<1204	1204-1806	1806-2167	2167-2287	2287-2408	2408-2528	2528-3009	>3009
FRASNO, EL	<2042	2042-3062	3062-3675	3675-3879	3879-4083	4083-4287	4287-5104	>5104

FUENTES DE JILOCA	<1382	1382-2073	2073-2488	2488-2626	2626-2764	2764-2902	2902-3455	>3455
GODOJOS	<5251	5251-7877	7877-9452	9452-9977	9977-10502	10502-11028	11028-13128	>13128
IBDES	<1520	1520-2279	2279-2735	2735-2887	2887-3039	3039-3191	3191-3799	>3799
JARABA	<1555	1555-2332	2332-2799	2799-2954	2954-3110	3110-3265	3265-3887	>3887
MALANQUILLA	<1485	1485-2228	2228-2674	2674-2822	2822-2971	2971-3119	3119-3713	>3713
MALUENDA	<1295	1295-1943	1943-2332	2332-2461	2461-2591	2591-2720	2720-3238	>3238
MARA	<1857	1857-2786	2786-3343	3343-3529	3529-3715	3715-3900	3900-4643	>4643
MIEDES DE ARAGÓN	<1497	1497-2245	2245-2694	2694-2844	2844-2994	2994-3143	3143-3742	>3742
MONREAL DE ARIZA	<1443	1443-2165	2165-2598	2598-2742	2742-2887	2887-3031	3031-3608	>3608
MONTERDE	<944	944-1416	1416-1700	1700-1794	1794-1889	1889-1983	1983-2361	>2361
MONTÓN	<1763	1763-2644	2644-3173	3173-3349	3349-3525	3525-3701	3701-4406	>4406
MORATA DE JILOCA	<1678	1678-2517	2517-3020	3020-3188	3188-3356	3356-3524	3524-4195	>4195
MORÉS	<3814	3814-5721	5721-6866	6866-7247	7247-7628	7628-8010	8010-9535	>9535
MOROS	<994	994-1491	1491-1790	1790-1889	1889-1988	1988-2088	2088-2486	>2486
MUNÉBREGA	<1584	1584-2376	2376-2852	2852-3010	3010-3168	3168-3327	3327-3960	>3960
NIGÜELLA	<1362	1362-2043	2043-2451	2451-2587	2587-2723	2723-2860	2860-3404	>3404
NUÉVALOS	<1879	1879-2819	2819-3383	3383-3571	3571-3759	3759-3947	3947-4699	>4699
OLVÉS	<1146	1146-1719	1719-2063	2063-2178	2178-2292	2292-2407	2407-2865	>2865
ORERA	<1668	1668-2503	2503-3003	3003-3170	3170-3337	3337-3504	3504-4171	>4171
PARACUELLOS DE JILOCA	<2981	2981-4472	4472-5367	5367-5665	5665-5963	5963-6261	6261-7453	>7453
PARACUELLOS DE LA RIBERA	<1330	1330-1996	1996-2395	2395-2528	2528-2661	2661-2794	2794-3326	>3326
POZUEL DE ARIZA	<3256	3256-4884	4884-5861	5861-6187	6187-6512	6512-6838	6838-8140	>8140
RUESCA	<1271	1271-1906	1906-2287	2287-2414	2414-2541	2541-2668	2668-3177	>3177
SABIÑÁN	<1406	1406-2109	2109-2530	2530-2671	2671-2811	2811-2952	2952-3514	>3514
SEDILES	<3538	3538-5308	5308-6369	6369-6723	6723-7077	7077-7431	7431-8846	>8846
SISAMÓN	<3578	3578-5366	5366-6440	6440-6797	6797-7155	7155-7513	7513-8944	>8944
TERRER	<2264	2264-3396	3396-4075	4075-4302	4302-4528	4528-4755	4755-5660	>5660
TOBED	<1802	1802-2703	2703-3244	3244-3424	3424-3604	3604-3785	3785-4506	>4506
TORRALBA DE RIBOTA	<1669	1669-2503	2503-3003	3003-3170	3170-3337	3337-3504	3504-4171	>4171
TORREHERMOSA	<2237	2237-3356	3356-4027	4027-4251	4251-4475	4475-4699	4699-5594	>5594
TORRELAPAJA	<2064	2064-3095	3095-3715	3715-3921	3921-4127	4127-4334	4334-5159	>5159
TORRIJO DE LA CAÑADA	<1939	1939-2909	2909-3491	3491-3685	3685-3879	3879-4073	4073-4848	>4848
VALTORRES	<2393	2393-3590	3590-4308	4308-4547	4547-4787	4787-5026	5026-5983	>5983
VELILLA DE JILOCA	<1466	1466-2198	2198-2638	2638-2785	2785-2931	2931-3078	3078-3664	>3664

VILLAFELICHE	<1547	1547-2320	2320-2784	2784-2939	2939-3094	3094-3248	3248-3867	>3867
VILLALBA DE PEREJIL	<1530	1530-2294	2294-2753	2753-2906	2906-3059	3059-3212	3212-3824	>3824
VILLALENGUA	<1496	1496-2244	2244-2693	2693-2843	2843-2992	2992-3142	3142-3740	>3740
VILLARROYA DE LA SIERRA	<1974	1974-2960	2960-3553	3553-3750	3750-3947	3947-4145	4145-4934	>4934
VILUEÑA, LA	<1267	1267-1901	1901-2281	2281-2408	2408-2535	2535-2662	2662-3169	>3169

Table 3. CO₂ emissions label per household and per municipality (kg CO₂/kWh/year)

Municipality	A+	A	B	C	D	E	F	G
ABANTO	<492	492-738	738-886	886-935	935-984	984-1034	1034-1230	>1230
ALARBA	<393	393-590	590-708	708-747	747-786	786-826	826-983	>983
ALCONCHEL DE ARIZA	<840	840-1260	1260-1511	1511-1595	1595-1679	1679-1763	1763-2099	>2099
ALHAMA DE ARAGÓN	<524	524-786	786-943	943-995	995-1048	1048-1100	1100-1310	>1310
ANIÑÓN	<636	636-954	954-1145	1145-1208	1208-1272	1272-1335	1335-1590	>1590
ARÁNDIGA	<622	622-932	932-1119	1119-1181	1181-1243	1243-1305	1305-1554	>1554
ARIZA	<558	558-837	837-1004	1004-1060	1060-1116	1116-1172	1172-1395	>1395
ATECA	<573	573-860	860-1032	1032-1089	1089-1147	1147-1204	1204-1433	<1433
BELMONTE DE GRACIÁN	<354	354-530	530-637	637-672	672-707	707-743	743-884	>884
BERDEJO	<330	330-494	494-593	593-626	626-659	659-692	692-824	>824
BIJUESCA	<566	566-849	849-1019	1019-1075	1075-1132	1132-1189	1189-1415	>1415
BORDALBA	<431	431-646	646-775	775-818	818-861	861-904	904-1077	>1077
BUBIERCA	<594	594-890	890-1069	1069-1128	1128-1187	1187-1247	1247-1484	>1484
CABOLAFUENTE	<1176	1176-1764	1764-2117	2117-2234	2234-2352	2352-2469	2469-2940	>2940
CALATAYUD	<660	660-990	990-1188	1188-1254	1254-1320	1320-1386	1386-1650	>1650
CALMARZA	<673	673-1010	1010-1212	1212-1279	1279-1347	1347-1414	1414-1684	>1684
CAMPILLO DE ARAGÓN	<370	370-554	554-665	665-702	702-739	739-776	776-924	>924
CARENAS	<728	728-1091	1091-1310	1310-1382	1382-1455	1455-1528	1528-1819	>1819
CASTEJÓN DE ALARBA	<402	402-603	603-723	723-763	763-803	803-844	844-1004	>1004
CASTEJÓN DE LAS ARMAS	<438	438-656	656-788	788-831	831-875	875-919	919-1094	>1094
CERVERA DE LA CAÑADA	<454	454-681	681-818	818-863	863-908	908-954	954-1135	<1135
CETINA	<522	522-783	783-939	939-991	991-1044	1044-1096	1096-1305	>1305
CIMBALLA	<562	562-843	843-1012	1012-1068	1068-1125	1125-1181	1181-1406	>1406
CLARÉS DE RIBOTA	<451	451-676	676-811	811-856	856-901	901-946	946-1126	>1126
CODOS	<744	744-1116	1116-1340	1340-1414	1414-1489	1489-1563	1563-1861	>1861
CONTAMINA	<750	750-1125	1125-1350	1350-1425	1425-1500	1500-1576	1576-1876	>1876
EMBED DE ARIZA	<370	370-554	554-665	665-702	702-739	739-776	776-924	>924
FRASNO, EL	<627	627-940	940-1128	1128-1191	1191-1254	1254-1316	1316-1567	>1567

FUENTES DE JILOCA	<424	424-636	636-764	764-806	806-849	849-891	891-1061	>1061
GODOJOS	<1612	1612-2418	2418-2902	2902-3063	3063-3224	3224-3385	3385-4030	>4030
IBDES	<467	467-700	700-840	840-886	886-933	933-980	980-1166	>1166
JARABA	<477	477-716	716-859	859-907	907-955	955-1002	1002-1193	>1193
MALANQUILLA	<456	456-684	684-821	821-866	866-912	912-958	958-1140	>1140
MALUENDA	<398	398-597	597-716	716-756	756-795	795-835	835-994	>994
MARA	<570	570-855	855-1026	1026-1083	1083-1140	1140-1197	1197-1425	>1425
MIEDES DE ARAGÓN	<460	460-689	689-827	827-873	873-919	919-965	965-1149	>1149
MONREAL DE ARIZA	<443	443-665	665-798	798-842	842-886	886-930	930-1108	>1108
MONTERDE	<290	290-435	435-522	522-551	551-580	580-609	609-725	>725
MONTÓN	<541	541-812	812-974	974-1028	1028-1082	1082-1136	1136-1353	>1353
MORATA DE JILOCA	<515	515-773	773-927	927-979	979-1030	1030-1082	1082-1288	>1288
MORÉS	<1171	1171-1756	1756-2108	2108-2225	2225-2342	2342-2459	2459-2927	>2927
MOROS	<305	305-458	458-549	549-580	580-610	610-641	641-763	>763
MUNÉBREGA	<486	486-730	730-875	875-924	924-973	973-1021	1021-1216	>1216
NIGÜELLA	<418	418-627	627-752	752-794	794-836	836-878	878-1045	>1045
NUÉVALOS	<577	577-865	865-1039	1039-1096	1096-1154	1154-1212	1212-1442	>1442
OLVÉS	<352	352-528	528-633	633-669	669-704	704-739	739-880	>880
ORERA	<512	512-768	768-922	922-973	973-1024	1024-1076	1076-1281	>1281
PARACUELLOS DE JILOCA	<915	915-1373	1373-1648	1648-1739	1739-1831	1831-1922	1922-2288	>2288
PARACUELLOS DE LA RIBERA	<408	408-613	613-735	735-776	776-817	817-858	858-1021	>1021
POZUEL DE ARIZA	<1000	1000-1499	1499-1799	1799-1899	1899-1999	1999-2099	2099-2499	>2499
RUESCA	<390	390-585	585-702	702-741	741-780	780-819	819-975	>975
SABIÑÁN	<432	432-647	647-777	777-820	820-863	863-906	906-1079	>1079
SEDILES	<1086	1086-1629	1629-1955	1955-2064	2064-2173	2173-2281	2281-2716	>2716
SISAMÓN	<1098	1098-1647	1647-1977	1977-2087	2087-2197	2197-2306	2306-2746	>2746
TERRER	<695	695-1043	1043-1251	1251-1321	1321-1390	1390-1460	1460-1738	>1738
TOBED	<553	553-830	830-996	996-1051	1051-1107	1107-1162	1162-1383	>1383
TORRALBA DE RIBOTA	<512	512-768	768-922	922-973	973-1024	1024-1076	1076-1281	>1281
TORREHERMOSA	<687	687-1030	1030-1236	1236-1305	1305-1374	1374-1442	1442-1717	>1717
TORRELAPAJA	<634	634-950	950-1140	1140-1204	1204-1267	1267-1330	1330-1584	>1584
TORRIJO DE LA CAÑADA	<595	595-893	893-1072	1072-1131	1131-1191	1191-1250	1250-1488	>1488
VALTORRES	<735	735-1102	1102-1323	1323-1396	1396-1470	1470-1543	1543-1837	>1837
VELILLA DE JILOCA	<450	450-675	675-810	810-855	855-900	900-945	945-1125	>1125
VILLAFELICHE	<475	475-712	712-855	855-902	902-950	950-997	997-1187	>1187
VILLALBA DE PEREJIL	<470	470-704	704-845	845-892	892-939	939-986	986-1174	>1174
VILLALENGUA	<459	459-689	689-827	827-873	873-919	919-965	965-1148	>1148
VILLARROYA DE LA SIERRA	<606	606-909	909-1091	1091-1151	1151-1212	1212-1272	1272-1515	>1515
VILUEÑA, LA	<389	389-584	584-700	700-739	739-778	778-817	817-973	>973

Definition of the equations to calculate the labels.

As done for the residential case, the calculation of the current energy use is explained in this section. The equation considered is shown in equation (1), where the electricity consumption is per house.

$$\text{Carbon Footprint}_{\text{electricity consumption}} = \text{electricity consumption} \cdot \text{EF}_{\text{electricity consumption}} \quad (1)$$

The different energy sources used for supplying the residential sector can be found in Table 4, where the emission factor is also shown [7]. Moreover, renewable energy sources can be used for energy supply in house. EFs for Renewable sources can be found in Table 5.

Table 4 Fuel emission factors

Fuel	Emission Factor (kg CO ₂ /kWh)
Natural gas	0.202
Liquified Petroleum Gases (LPG)	0.227
Natural Gas Liquids (NGL)	0.231
Diesel	0.267
Gasoline	0.249
Coal	0.354
Heating oil	0.267

Table 5 Heating renewable energy sources emission factors

Renewable energy source	Emission Factor (kg CO ₂ /kWh)
Biomass	0.118
Locally-produced biomass	0.000
Geothermal	0.050
Solar thermal	0.040
District heating	0.268

2.2.2 Industries

Tables 6 and 7 show the baseline levels for industries in terms of energy consumption and emissions, respectively. The EF used for the CO₂ emissions label is the national grid emissions factor due to most of the industries use electricity as the energy source in Spain [8].

Table 6. Label for the energy consumption per industry and municipality (kWh/year)

Municipality	A+	A	B	C	D	E	F	G
ALHAMA DE ARAGÓN	<140047	14047-210070	210070-252085	252085-266089	266089-280094	280094-294099	294099-350117	>350117
ANIÑÓN	<18553	18553-27830	27830-33396	33396-35251	35251-37107	37107-38962	38962-46383	>46383
ARÁNDIGA	<6243	6243-9365	9365-11238	11238-11862	11862-12487	12487-13111	13111-15608	>15608
ARIZA	<48379	48379-72569	72569-87082	87082-91920	91920-96758	96758-101596	101596-120948	>120948
ATECA	<62440	62440-93660	93660-112392	112392-118636	118636-124880	124880-131124	131124-156100	>156100
CALATAYUD	<43980	43980-65970	65970-79164	79164-83562	83562-87960	87960-92358	92358-109951	>109951

CETINA	<8656	8656-12983	12983-15580	15580-16446	16446-17311	17311-18177	18177-21639	>21639
EL FRASNO	<12030	12030-18045	18045-21654	21654-22857	22857-24060	24060-25263	25263-30075	>30075
MORÉS	<19559	19559-29339	29339-35207	35207-37163	37163-39119	39119-41074	41074-48898	>48898
MUNÉBREGA	<5338	5338-8007	8007-9609	9609-10143	10143-10676	10676-11210	11210-13346	>13346
SABIÑÁN	<40898	40898-61347	61347-73616	73616-77706	77706-81796	81796-85886	85886-102245	>102245
LA VILUEÑA	<537	537-805	805-966	966-1020	1020-1073	1073-1127	1127-1342	>1342

Table 7. CO₂ emissions label per industry and municipality (kg CO₂/kWh/year)

Municipality	A+	A	B	C	D	E	F	G
ALHAMA DE ARAGÓN	<42994	42994-64492	64492-77390	77390-81689	81689-85989	85989-90288	90288-107486	>107486
ANIÑÓN	<5696	5696-8544	8544-10253	10253-10822	10822-11392	11392-11961	11961-14240	>14240
ARÁNDIGA	<1917	1917-2875	2875-3450	3450-3642	3642-3833	3833-4025	4025-4792	>4792
ARIZA	<14852	14852-22279	22279-26734	26734-28219	28219-29705	29705-31190	31190-37131	>37131
ATECA	<19169	19169-28754	28754-34504	34504-36421	36421-38338	38338-40255	40255-47923	>47923
CALATAYUD	<13502	13502-20253	20253-24303	24303-25654	25654-27004	27004-28354	28354-33755	>33755
CETINA	<2657	2657-3986	3986-4783	4783-5049	5049-5314	5314-5580	5580-6643	>6643
EL FRASNO	<3693	3693-5540	5540-6648	6648-7017	7017-7386	7386-7756	7756-9233	>9233
MORÉS	<6005	6005-9007	9007-10808	10808-11409	11409-12009	12009-12610	12610-15012	>15012
MUNÉBREGA	<1639	1639-2458	2458-2950	2950-3114	3114-3278	3278-3442	3442-4097	>4097
SABIÑÁN	<12556	12556-18834	18834-22600	22600-23856	23856-25111	25111-26367	26367-31389	>31389
LA VILUEÑA	<165	165-247	247-297	297-313	313-329	329-346	346-412	>412

Definition of the equations to calculate the labels.

As done for the residential case, the calculation of the current energy use is explained in this section. The equation considered is equation (1).

Industries are also supplied by other energy sources such as natural gas, diesel, gasoline, etc. The EFs of these sources [7] can be found in Table 8. Moreover, renewable energy sources can be used for energy supply in industries. EFs for Renewable sources can be found in Table 5.

Table 8 Fuel emission factors

Fuel	Emission Factor (kg CO ₂ /kWh)
Natural gas	0.202
Liquified Petroleum Gases (LPG)	0.227
Natural Gas Liquids (NGL)	0.231
Diesel	0.267
Gasoline	0.249
Coal	0.354

2.2.3 Services

The calculation of the environmental impact of the services follows the same approach as the industry sector, where the label will be associated with the townhall, schools, street lighting, shops, sports centre, etc. and these entities will be 'Near-Zero Emissions' entities if their emissions belong to that level. Table 9 shows the label associated with the energy consumption of the service sector, and table 10, the emissions associated to this sector. As done with the industries, the EF used is the one corresponding to the national electricity grid [8].

Table 9. Label for the energy consumption per service and municipality (kWh/year)

Municipality	A+	A	B	C	D	E	F	G
ABANTO	<1263	1263-2172	2172-2323	2323-2399	2399-2525	2525-2652	2652-2879	>2879
ALARBA	<1259	1259-2165	2165-2316	2316-2392	2392-2517	2517-2643	2643-2870	>2870
ALCONCHEL DE ARIZA	<2006	2006-3450	3450-3690	3690-3811	3811-4011	4011-4212	4212-4573	>4573
ALHAMA DE ARAGÓN	<13861	13861-23841	23841-25504	25504-26336	26336-27722	27722-29108	29108-31603	>31603
ANIÑÓN	<3217	3217-5534	5534-5920	5920-6113	6113-6435	6435-6756	6756-7336	>7336
ARÁNDIGA	<4439	4439-7635	7635-8167	8167-8434	8434-8878	8878-9322	9322-10121	>10121
ARIZA	<16166	16166-27805	27805-29745	29745-30715	30715-32332	32332-33948	33948-36858	>36858
ATECA	<6304	6304-10843	10843-11599	11599-11978	11978-12608	12608-13238	13238-14373	>14373
BELMONTE DE GRACIÁN	<2446	2446-4207	4207-4501	4501-4647	4647-4892	4892-5136	5136-5577	>5577
BIJUESCA	<2041	2041-3510	3510-3755	3755-3877	3877-4081	4081-4285	4285-4653	>4653
BUBIERCA	<73305	73305-126085	126085-134882	134882-139280	139280-146610	146610-153941	153941-167136	>167136
CALATAYUD	<13074	13074-22487	22487-24056	24056-24840	24840-26148	26148-27455	27455-29808	>29808
CARENAS	<3962	3962-6814	6814-7290	7290-7527	7527-7924	7924-8320	8320-9033	>9033
CASTEJÓN DE LAS ARMAS	<2363	2363-4064	4064-4347	4347-4489	4489-4725	4725-4962	4962-5387	>5387
CERVERA DE LA CAÑADA	<1931	1931-3322	3322-3554	3554-3670	3670-3863	3863-4056	4056-4404	>4404
CETINA	<6624	6624-11394	11394-12189	12189-12586	12586-13249	13249-13911	13911-15103	>15103
CIMBALLA	<3610	3610-6209	6209-6643	6643-6859	6859-7220	7220-7581	7581-8231	>8231
CLARÉS DE RIBOTA	<3481	3481-5987	5987-6405	6405-6614	6614-6962	6962-7310	7310-7936	>7936
CODOS	<2277	2277-3917	3917-4190	4190-4327	4327-4555	4555-4783	4783-5193	>5193
EMBED DE ARIZA	<1491	1491-2565	2565-2744	2744-2833	2833-2982	2982-3132	3132-3400	>3400
FRASNO, EL	<16149	16149-27775	27775-29713	29713-30682	30682-32297	32297-33912	33912-36819	>36819
FUENTES DE JILOCA	<3237	3237-5568	5568-5956	5956-6150	6150-6474	6474-6798	6798-7381	>7381
GODOJOS	<1504	1504-2587	2587-2768	2768-2858	2858-3008	3008-3159	3159-3429	>3429
IBDES	<3690	3690-6346	6346-6789	6789-7010	7010-7379	7379-7748	7748-8412	>8412
JARABA	<16666	16666-28666	28666-30666	30666-31666	31666-33332	33332-34999	34999-37999	>37999
MALANQUILLA	<2824	2824-4858	4858-5197	5197-5366	5366-5648	5648-5931	5931-6439	>6439

MALUENDA	<14543	14543-25013	25013-26758	26752-27631	27631-29085	29085-30539	30539-33157	>33157
MARA	<2577	2577-4433	4433-4743	4743-4897	4897-5155	5155-5413	5413-5877	>5877
MIEDES DE ARAGÓN	<4685	4685-8058	8058-8621	8621-8902	8902-9370	9370-9839	9839-10682	>10682
MONREAL DE ARIZA	<5211	5211-8963	8963-9588	9588-9901	9901-10422	10422-10943	10943-11881	>11881
MONTERDE	<3704	3704-6370	6370-6815	6815-7037	7037-7407	7407-7778	7778-8444	>8444
MONTÓN	<4104	4104-7058	7058-7550	7550-7797	7797-8207	8207-8617	8617-9356	>9356
MORATA DE JILOCA	<81992	81992-141025	141025-150864	150864-155784	155784-163983	163983-172182	172182-186941	>186941
MORÉS	<29541	29541-50810	50810-54355	54355-56127	56127-59081	59081-62035	62035-67352	>67352
MOROS	<9566	9566-16453	16453-17601	17601-18175	18175-19132	19132-20088	20088-21810	>21810
MUNÉBREGA	<6127	6127-10539	10539-11275	11275-11642	11642-12255	12255-12868	12868-13971	>13971
NIGÜELLA	<2808	2808-4829	4829-5166	5166-5334	5334-5615	5615-5896	5896-6401	>6401
NUÉVALOS	<28019	28019-48193	48193-51555	51555-53236	53236-56038	56038-58840	58840-63883	>63883
OLVÉS	<1523	1523-2620	2620-2803	2803-2895	2895-3047	3047-3199	3199-3474	>3474
ORERA	<1445	1445-2485	2485-2659	2659-2745	2745-2890	2890-3034	3034-3295	>3295
PARACUELLOS DE JILOCA	<15670	15670-26952	26952-28833	28833-29773	29773-31340	31340-32907	32907-35728	>35728
PARACUELLOS DE LA RIBERA	<3116	3116-5360	5360-5734	5734-5921	5921-6233	6233-6545	6545-7106	>7106
SABIÑÁN	<9858	9858-16957	16957-18140	18140-18731	18731-19717	19717-20703	20703-22477	>22477
SEDILES	<986	986-1696	1696-1815	1815-1874	1874-1972	1972-2071	2071-2249	>2249
TERRER	<361190	361190-621247	621247-664590	664590-686261	686261-722380	722380-758499	758499-823513	>823513
TOBED	<2318	2318-3987	3987-4265	4265-4404	4404-4636	4636-4868	4868-5285	>5285
TORRALBA DE RIBOTA	<2843	2843-4889	4889-5231	5231-5401	5401-5685	5685-5970	5970-6481	>6481
TORREHERMOSA	<3457	3457-5946	5946-6361	6361-6569	6569-6914	6914-7260	7260-7882	>7882
TORRELAPAJA	<1587	1587-2730	2730-2920	2920-3015	3015-3174	3174-3333	3333-3618	>3618
TORRIJO DE LA CAÑADA	<3311	3311-5695	5695-6093	6093-6291	6291-6623	6623-6954	6954-7550	>7550
VALTORRES	<2848	2848-4898	4898-5239	5239-5410	5410-5695	5695-5980	5980-6492	>6492
VELILLA DE JILOCA	<2461	2461-4233	4233-4528	4528-4676	4676-4922	4922-5168	5168-5611	>5611
VILLAFELICHE	<3886	3886-6684	6684-7150	7150-7383	7383-7772	7772-8160	8160-8860	>8860
VILLALBA DE PEREJIL	<1611	1611-2771	2771-2965	2965-3061	3061-3222	3222-3383	3383-3673	>3673
VILLALENGUA	<6401	6401-11009	11009-11778	11778-12162	12162-12802	12802-13442	13442-14594	>14594

Table 10. CO₂ emissions label per service and municipality (kg CO₂/kWh/year)

Municipality	A+	A	B	C	D	E	F	G
ABANTO	<388	388-667	667-713	713-737	737-775	775-814	714-884	>884
ALARBA	<386	386-665	665-711	711-734	734-773	773-812	812-881	>881
ALCONCHEL DE ARIZA	<616	616-1059	1059-1133	1133-1170	1170-1231	1231-1293	1404	>1404
ALHAMA DE ARAGÓN	<4255	4255-7319	7319-7830	7830-8085	8085-8511	8511-8936	8936-9702	>9702

ANIÑÓN	<988	988-1699	1699-1817	1817-1877	1877-1975	1975-2074	2074-2252	>2252
ARÁNDIGA	<1363	1363-2344	2344-2507	2507-2589	2589-2725	2725-2862	2862-3107	>3107
ARIZA	<4963	4963-8536	8536-9132	9132-9430	9430-9926	9926-10422	10422-11315	>11315
ATECA	<1935	1935-3329	3329-3561	3561-3677	3677-3871	3871-4064	4064-4413	>4413
BELMONTE DE GRACIÁN	<751	751-1292	1292-1382	1382-1427	1427-1502	1502-1577	1577-1712	>1712
BIJUESCA	<626	626-1078	1078-1153	1153-1190	1190-1253	1253-1316	1316-1428	>1428
BUBIERCA	<22505	22505-38708	38708-41409	41409-42759	42759-45009	45009-47260	47260-51311	>51311
CALATAYUD	<4014	4014-6904	6904-7385	7385-7626	7626-8027	8027-8429	8429-9151	>9151
CARENAS	<1216	1216-2092	2092-2238	2238-2311	2311-2433	2433-2554	2554-2773	>2773
CASTEJÓN DE LAS ARMAS	<725	725-1248	1248-1335	1335-1378	1378-1451	1451-1523	1523-1654	>1654
CERVERA DE LA CAÑADA	<593	593-1020	1020-1091	1091-1127	1127-1186	1186-1245	1245-1352	>1352
CETINA	<2034	2034-3498	3498-3742	3742-3864	3864-4067	4067-4271	4271-4637	>4637
CIMBALLA	<1108	1108-1906	1906-2039	2039-2106	2106-2217	2217-2327	2327-2527	>2527
CLARÉS DE RIBOTA	<1069	1069-1838	1838-1966	1966-2030	2030-2137	2137-2244	2244-2436	>2436
CODOS	<699	699-1203	1203-1286	1286-1328	1328-1398	1398-1468	1468-1594	>1594
EMBED DE ARIZA	<458	458-787	787-842	842-870	870-916	916-961	961-1044	>1044
FRASNO, EL	<4958	4958-8527	8527-9122	9122-9419	9419-9915	9915-10411	10411-11303	>11303
FUENTES DE JILOCA	<994	994-1709	1709-1829	1829-1888	1888-1988	1988-2087	2087-2266	>2266
GODOJOS	<462	462-794	794-850	850-877	877-924	924-970	970-1053	>1053
IBDES	<1133	1133-1948	1948-2084	2084-2152	2152-2265	2265-2379	2379-2583	>2583
JARABA	<5116	5116-8800	8800-9414	9414-9721	9721-10233	10233-10745	10745-11666	>11666
MALANQUILLA	<867	867-1491	1491-1595	1595-1647	1647-1734	1734-1821	1821-1977	>1977
MALUENDA	<4465	4465-7679	7679-8215	8215-8483	8483-8929	8929-9376	9376-10179	>10179
MARA	<791	791-1361	1361-1456	1456-1503	1503-1583	1583-1662	1662-1804	>1804
MIEDES DE ARAGÓN	<1438	1438-2474	2474-2647	2647-2733	2733-2877	2877-3021	3021-3279	>3279
MONREAL DE ARIZA	<1600	1600-2752	2752-2944	2944-3040	3040-3200	3200-3360	3360-3648	>3648
MONTERDE	<1137	1137-1956	1956-2092	2092-2160	2160-2274	2274-2388	2388-2592	>2592
MONTÓN	<1260	1260-2167	2167-2318	2318-2394	2394-2520	2520-2646	2646-2872	>2872
MORATA DE JILOCA	<25171	25171-43295	43295-46315	46315-47826	47826-50343	50343-52860	52860-57391	>57391
MORÉS	<9069	9069-15599	15599-16687	16687-17231	17231-18138	18138-19045	19045-20677	>20677
MOROS	<2937	2937-5051	5051-5404	5404-5580	5580-5873	5873-6167	6167-6696	>6696
MUNÉBREGA	<1881	1881-3236	3236-3461	3461-3574	3574-3762	3762-3950	3950-4289	>4289
NIGÜELLA	<862	862-1482	1482-1586	1586-1638	1638-1724	1724-1810	1810-1965	>1965
NUÉVALOS	<8602	8602-14795	14795-15827	15827-16343	16343-17204	17204-18064	18064-19612	>19612
OLVÉS	<468	468-804	804-861	861-889	889-935	935-982	982-1066	>1066
ORERA	<444	444-763	763-816	816-843	843-887	887-932	932-1011	>1011

PARACUELLOS DE JILOCA	<4811	4811-8274	8274-8852	8852-9140	9140-9621	9621-10102	10102-10968	>10968
PARACUELLOS DE LA RIBERA	<957	957-1646	1646-1760	1760-1818	1818-1914	1914-2009	2009-2181	>2181
SABIÑÁN	<3027	3027-5206	5206-5569	5569-5750	5750-6053	6053-6356	6356-6901	>6901
SEDILES	<303	303-521	521-557	557-575	575-606	606-636	636-690	>690
TERRER	<110885	110885-190723	190723-204029	204029-210682	210682-221771	221771-232859	232859-252819	>252819
TOBED	<712	712-1224	1224-1309	1309-1352	1352-1423	1423-1494	1494-1623	>1623
TORRALBA DE RIBOTA	<873	873-1501	1501-1606	1606-1658	1658-1745	1745-1833	1833-1990	>1990
TORREHERMOSA	<1061	1061-1826	1826-1953	1953-2017	2017-2123	2123-2229	2229-2420	>2420
TORRELAPAJA	<487	487-838	838-896	896-926	926-974	974-1023	1023-1111	>1111
TORRIJO DE LA CAÑADA	<1017	1017-1749	1749-1870	1870-1931	1931-2033	2033-2135	2135-2318	>2318
VALTORRES	<874	874-1504	1504-1608	1608-1661	1661-1748	1748-1836	1836-1993	>1993
VELILLA DE JILOCA	<756	756-1299	1299-1390	1390-1435	1435-1511	1511-1587	1587-1723	>1723
VILLAFELICHE	<1193	1193-2052	2052-2195	2195-2267	2267-2386	2386-2505	2505-2720	>2720
VILLALBA DE PEREJIL	<495	495-851	851-910	910-940	940-989	989-1039	1039-1128	>1128
VILLALENGUA	<1965	1965-3380	3380-3616	3616-3734	3734-3930	3930-4127	4127-4480	>4480

Definition of the equations to calculate the labels.

The calculation for the services sector follows the same approach as the industry sector, using equation (1).

2.2.5 Municipalities

The calculation for the municipalities label is simple: the energy consumption of the municipality corresponds to the sum of the energy consumption of industries, services and households for each municipality, as shown in equation (2). Table 11 shows the energy consumption label for each municipality.

$$Energy\ cons_{municipality} = Energy\ cons_{industries} + Energy\ cons_{services} + Energy\ cons_{residential} \quad (2)$$

Table 11. Energy consumption label per municipality (kWh/year)

Municipality	A+	A	B	C	D	E	F	G
ABANTO	<95193	95193-147789	147789-172256	172256-180866	180866-190385	190385-199904	199904-232981	>232981
ALARBA	<100518	100518-155762	155762-181839	181839-190984	190984-201036	201036-211088	211088-246311	>246311
ALCONCHEL DE ARIZA	<135660	135660-214079	214079-246112	246112-257753	257753-271319	271319-284885	284885-328560	>328560
ALHAMA DE ARAGÓN	<4446471	4446471-6962447	6962447-8056874	8056874-8448295	8448295-8892943	8892943-9337590	9337590-10823438	>10823438
ANIÑÓN	<1218603	1218603-1883821	1883821-2203651	2203651-2315345	2315345-2437205	2437205-2559065	2559065-2990589	>2990589
ARÁNDIGA	<525177	525177-824874	824874-952065	952065-997836	997836-1050354	1050354-1102872	1102872-1275834	>1275834
ARIZA	<3776964	3776964-6081556	6081556-6874192	6874192-7176232	7176232-7553928	7553928-7931624	7931624-9026300	>9026300
ATECA	<4071201	4071201-6335636	6335636-7369768	7369768-7735282	7735282-8142402	8142402-8549522	8549522-9949168	>9949168

BELMONTE DE GRACIÁN	<146146	146146-229981	229981-265020	265020-277678	277678-292292	292292-306907	306907-354603	>354603
BERDEJO	<22762	22762-34143	34143-40972	40972-43248	43248-45524	45524-47800	47800-56905	>56905
BIJUESCA	<100280	100280-156256	156256-181565	181565-190532	190532-200560	200560-210588	210588-244864	>244864
BORDALBA	<34785	34785-52178	52178-62613	62613-66092	66092-69571	69571-73049	73049-86963	>86963
BUBIERCA	<938445	938445-1601193	1601193-1724387	1724387-1783045	1783045-1876889	1876889-1970734	1970734-2152586	>2152586
CABOLAFUENTE	<58221	58221-87331	87331-104797	104797-110620	110620-116442	116442-122264	122264-145552	>145552
CALATAYUD	<43024202	43024202-68200642	68200642-78109807	78109807-81745984	81745984-86048404	86048404-90350824	90350824-103896166	>103896166
CALMARZA	<67561	67561-101342	101342-121610	121610-128366	128366-135122	135122-141878	141878-168903	>168903
CAMPILLO DE ARAGÓN	<67904	67904-101856	101856-122228	122228-129018	129018-135808	135808-142599	142599-169760	>169760
CARENAS	<266057	266057-421747	421747-483022	483022-505508	505508-532113	532113-558719	558719-642480	>642480
CASTEJÓN DE ALARBA	<49727	49727-74590	74590-89508	89508-94480	94480-99453	99453-104426	104426-124316	>124316
CASTEJÓN DE LAS ARMAS	<93014	93014-147318	147318-168843	168843-176727	176727-186028	186028-195330	195330-224739	>224739
CERVERA DE LA CAÑADA	<257431	257431-402293	402293-466312	466312-489119	489119-514862	514862-540606	540606-627432	>627432
CETINA	<943907	943907-1500387	1500387-1714402	1714402-1793424	1793424-1887815	1887815-1982206	1982206-2275243	>2275243
CIMBALLA	<147766	147766-235945	235945-268578	268578-280755	280755-295532	295532-310309	310309-355119	>355119
CLARÉS DE RIBOTA	<85254	85254-136305	136305-154990	154990-161983	161983-170509	170509-179034	179034-204713	>204713
CODOS	<259124	259124-406223	406223-469612	469612-492336	492336-518249	518249-544161	544161-630275	>630275
CONTAMINA	<35190	35190-52786	52786-63343	63343-66862	66862-70381	70381-73900	73900-87976	>87976
EMBID DE ARIZA	<40526	40526-64726	64726-73663	73663-76999	76999-81052	81052-85105	85105-97378	>97378
FRASNO, EL	<1601635	1601635-2651139	2651139-2928158	2928158-3043106	3043106-3203269	3203269-3363433	3363433-3755399	>3755399
FUENTES DE JILOCA	<201997	201997-320800	320800-366832	366832-383795	383795-403995	403995-424194	424194-487189	>487189
GODOJOS	<111120	111120-174952	174952-201519	201519-211127	211127-222239	222239-233351	233351-269527	>269527
IBDES	<464736	464736-738502	738502-844052	844052-882999	882999-929473	929473-975946	975946-1120443	>1120443
JARABA	<918137	918137-1534867	1534867-1681312	1681312-1744460	1744460-1836274	1836274-1928088	1928088-2137682	>2137682
MALANQUILLA	<132097	132097-212437	212437-240373	240373-250985	250985-264195	264195-277404	277404-315953	>315953
MALUENDA	<1262894	1262894-2054309	2054309-2302294	2302294-2399498	2399498-2525787	2525787-2652077	2652077-2997266	>2997266
MARA	<184185	184185-287051	287051-333492	333492-349951	349951-368370	368370-386788	386788-449688	>449688
MIEDES DE ARAGÓN	<436710	436710-688049	688049-792076	792076-829750	829750-873421	873421-917092	917092-1058792	>1058792
MONREAL DE ARIZA	<310551	310551-505952	505952-566287	566287-590047	590047-621102	621102-652157	652157-736252	>736252
MONTERDE	<167966	167966-265801	265801-304858	304858-319136	319136-335932	335932-352729	352729-406064	>406064
MONTÓN	<119166	119166-188679	188679-216304	216304-226415	226415-238332	238332-250248	250248-287984	>287984
MORATA DE JILOCA	<2385587	2385587-4065410	4065410-4382607	4382607-4532615	4532615-4771174	4771174-5009732	5009732-5476937	>5476937
MORÉS	<2391769	2391769-3932097	3932097-4367811	4367811-4544362	4544362-4783539	4783539-5022716	5022716-5634981	>5634981
MOROS	<444859	444859-730423	730423-812225	812225-845232	845232-889718	889718-934204	934204-1049013	>1049013

MUNÉBREGA	<664063	664063-1044624	1044624-1204137	1204137-1261719	1261719-1328126	1328126-1394532	1394532-1611627	>1611627
NIGÜELLA	<76175	76175-121674	121674-138463	138463-144732	144732-152350	152350-159967	159967-183026	>183026
NUÉVALOS	<1310553	1310553-2200067	2200067-2401584	2401584-2490050	2490050-2621106	2621106-2752161	2752161-3042144	>3042144
OLVÉS	<73446	73446-114526	114526-132994	132994-139547	139547-146891	146891-154236	154236-179257	>179257
ORERA	<106433	106433-164418	164418-192447	192447-202223	202223-212867	212867-223510	223510-261315	>261315
PARACUELLOS DE JILOCA	<1189380	1189380-1890940	1890940-2160315	2160315-2259822	2259822-2378760	2378760-2497698	2497698-2866580	>2866580
PARACUELLOS DE LA RIBERA	<151730	151730-241308	241308-275608	275608-288288	288288-303461	303461-318634	318634-365613	>365613
POZUEL DE ARIZA	<31259	31259-46889	46889-56267	56267-59393	59393-62519	62519-65645	65645-78148	>78148
RUESCA	<37104	37104-55657	55657-66788	66788-70498	70498-74209	74209-77919	77919-92761	>92761
SABIÑÁN	<1570527	1570527-2492429	2492429-2851792	2851792-2984002	2984002-3141054	3141054-3298107	3298107-3789679	>3789679
SEILES	<163409	163409-248367	248367-294727	294727-310476	310476-326817	326817-343158	343158-405267	>405267
SISAMÓN	<51517	51517-77275	77275-92730	92730-97881	97881-103033	103033-108185	108185-128791	>128791
TERRER	<16363285	16363285-28041248	28041248-30089608	30089608-31090242	31090242-32726571	32726571-34362899	34362899-37411894	>37411894
TOBED	<247033	247033-386358	386358-447534	447534-469363	469363-494066	494066-518769	518769-601773	>601773
TORRALBA DE RIBOTA	<192365	192365-303558	303558-348987	348987-365494	365494-384731	384731-403967	403967-465904	>465904
TORREHERMOSA	<99782	99782-158039	158039-181129	181129-189586	189586-199564	199564-209542	209542-241089	>241089
TORRELAPAJA	<46347	46347-73362	73362-84124	84124-88060	88060-92695	92695-97330	97330-112028	>112028
TORRIJO DE LA CAÑADA	<319197	319197-507206	507206-579720	579720-606474	606474-638393	638393-670313	670313-769581	>769581
VALTORRES	<103050	103050-163345	163345-187084	187084-195794	195794-206099	206099-216404	216404-248854	>248854
VELILLA DE JILOCA	<107264	107264-169017	169017-194551	194551-203801	203801-214528	214528-225254	225254-260038	>260038
VILLAFELICHE	<217795	217795-348065	348065-395917	395917-413811	413811-435590	435590-457370	457370-523115	>523115
VILLALBA DE PEREJIL	<84127	84127-131508	131508-152396	152396-159842	159842-168255	168255-176668	176668-205002	>205002
VILLALENGUA	<381082	381082-609644	609644-692861	692861-724056	724056-762164	762164-800273	800273-914684	>914684
VILLARROYA DE LA SIERRA	<581766	581766-913276	913276-1054565	1054565-1105355	1105355-1163531	1163531-1221708	1221708-1413787	>1413787
VILUEÑA, LA	<62177	62177-93265	93265-111918	111918-118136	118136-124353	124353-130571	130571-155441	>155441

Table 12 shows the label for the emissions of each municipality, calculated following the same approach as the energy consumption label.

Table 12. CO₂ emissions label per municipality (kg CO₂/kWh/year)

Municipality	A+	A	B	C	D	E	F	G
ABANTO	<29224	29224-45371	45371-52883	52883-55526	55526-58448	58448-61371	61371-71525	>71525
ALARBA	<30859	30859-47819	47819-55825	55825-58632	58632-61718	61718-64804	64804-75617	>75617
ALCONCHEL DE ARIZA	<41647	41647-65722	65722-75557	75557-79130	79130-83295	83295-87460	87460-100868	>100868
ALHAMA DE ARAGÓN	<1365067	1365067-2137471	2137471-2473460	2473460-2593627	2593627-2730133	2730133-2866640	2866640-3322796	>3322796
ANIÑÓN	<374111	374111-578333	578333-676521	676521-710811	710811-748222	748222-785633	785633-918111	>918111

ARÁNDIGA	<161229	161229-253236	253236-292284	292284-306336	306336-322459	322459-338582	338582-391681	>391681
ARIZA	<1159528	1159528-1867038	1867038-2110377	2110377-2203103	2203103-2319056	2319056-2435009	2435009-2771074	>2771074
ATECA	<1249859	1249859-1945040	1945040-2262519	2262519-2374732	2374732-2499717	2499717-2624703	2624703-3054395	>3054395
BELMONTE DE GRACIÁN	<44867	44867-70604	70604-81361	81361-85247	85247-89734	89734-94220	94220-108863	>108863
BERDEJO	<6988	6988-10482	10482-12578	12578-13277	13277-13976	13976-14675	14675-17470	>17470
BIJUESCA	<30786	30786-47971	47971-55740	55740-58493	58493-61572	61572-64650	64650-75173	>75173
BORDALBA	<10679	10679-16019	16019-19222	19222-20290	20290-21358	21358-22426	22426-26698	>26698
BUBIERCA	<288103	288103-491566	491566-529387	529387-547395	547395-576205	576205-605015	605015-660844	>660844
CABOLAFUENTE	<17874	17874-26811	26811-32173	32173-33960	33960-35748	35748-37535	37535-44684	>44684
CALATAYUD	<13208430	13208430-20937597	20937597-23979711	23979711-25096017	25096017-26416860	26416860-27737703	27737703-31896123	>31896123
CALMARZA	<20741	20741-31112	31112-37334	37334-39408	39408-41483	41483-43557	43557-51853	>51853
CAMPILLO DE ARAGÓN	<20847	20847-31270	31270-37524	37524-39609	39609-41693	41693-43778	43778-52116	>52116
CARENAS	<81679	81679-129476	129476-148288	148288-155191	155191-163359	163359-171527	171527-197241	>197241
CASTEJÓN DE ALARBA	<15266	15266-22899	22899-27479	27479-29005	29005-30532	30532-32059	32059-38165	>38165
CASTEJÓN DE LAS ARMAS	<28555	28555-45227	45227-51835	51835-54255	54255-57111	57111-59966	59966-68995	>68995
CERVERA DE LA CAÑADA	<79031	79031-123504	123504-143158	143158-150160	150160-158063	158063-165966	165966-192622	>192622
CETINA	<289780	289780-460619	460619-526321	526321-550581	550581-579559	579559-608537	608537-698499	>698499
CIMBALLA	<45364	45364-72435	72435-82453	82453-86192	86192-90728	90728-95265	95265-109022	>109022
CLARÉS DE RIBOTA	<26173	26173-41846	41846-47582	47582-49729	49729-52346	52346-54964	54964-62847	>62847
CODOS	<79551	79551-124710	124710-144171	144171-151147	151147-159102	159102-167057	167057-193494	>193494
CONTAMINA	<10803	10803-16205	16205-19446	19446-20527	20527-21607	21607-22687	22687-27009	>27009
EMBID DE ARIZA	<12441	12441-19871	19871-22614	22614-23639	23639-24883	24883-26127	26127-29895	>29895
FRASNO, EL	<491702	491702-813900	813900-898945	898945-934233	934233-983404	983404-1032574	1032574-1152908	>1152908
FUENTES DE JILOCA	<62013	62013-98486	98486-112617	112617-117825	117825-124026	124026-130228	130228-149567	>149567
GODOJOS	<34114	34114-53710	53710-61866	61866-64816	64816-68227	68227-71639	71639-82745	>82745
IBDES	<142674	142674-226720	226720-259124	259124-271081	271081-285348	285348-299616	299616-343976	>343976
JARABA	<281868	281868-471204	471204-516163	516163-535549	535549-563736	563736-591923	591923-656268	>656268
MALANQUILLA	<40554	40554-65218	65218-73795	73795-77052	77052-81108	81108-85163	85163-96997	>96997
MALUENDA	<387708	387708-630673	630673-706804	706804-736646	736646-775417	775417-814188	814188-920161	>920161
MARA	<56545	56545-88125	88125-102382	102382-107435	107435-113090	113090-118744	118744-138054	>138054
MIEDES DE ARAGÓN	<134070	134070-211231	211231-243167	243167-254733	254733-268140	268140-281547	281547-325049	>325049
MONREAL DE ARIZA	<95339	95339-155327	155327-173850	173850-181144	181144-190678	190678-200212	200212-226029	>226029
MONTERDE	<51566	51566-81601	81601-93591	93591-97975	97975-103131	103131-108288	108288-124662	>124662
MONTÓN	<36584	36584-57925	57925-66405	66405-69509	69509-73168	73168-76826	76826-88411	>88411

MORATA DE JILOCA	<732375	732375-1248081	1248081-1345460	1345460-1391513	1391513-1464750	1464750-1537988	1537988-1681420	>1681420
MORÉS	<734273	734273-1207154	1207154-1340918	1340918-1395119	1395119-1468546	1468546-1541974	1541974-1729939	>1729939
MOROS	<136572	136572-224240	224240-249353	249353-259486	259486-273143	273143-286801	286801-322047	>322047
MUNÉBREGA	<203867	203867-320699	320699-369670	369670-387348	387348-407735	407735-428121	428121-494770	>494770
NIGÜELLA	<23386	23386-37354	37354-42508	42508-44433	44433-46771	46771-49110	49110-56189	>56189
NUÉVALOS	<402340	402340-675421	675421-737286	737286-764445	764445-804679	804679-844913	844913-933938	>933938
OLVÉS	<22548	22548-35159	35159-40829	40829-42841	42841-45096	45096-47350	47350-55032	>55032
ORERA	<32675	32675-50476	50476-59081	59081-62083	62083-65350	65350-68618	68618-80224	>80224
PARACUELLOS DE JILOCA	<365140	365140-580518	580518-663217	663217-693765	693765-730279	730279-766793	766793-880040	>880040
PARACUELLOS DE LA RIBERA	<46581	46581-74082	74082-84612	84612-88504	88504-93162	93162-97821	97821-112243	>112243
POZUEL DE ARIZA	<9597	9597-14395	14395-17274	17274-18234	18234-19193	19193-20153	20153-23992	>23992
RUESCA	<11391	17087	20504	21643	22782	23921	28478	>28478
SABIÑÁN	<482152	482152-765176	765176-875500	875500-916088	916088-964304	964304-1012519	1012519-1163432	>1163432
SEILES	<50166	50166-76249	76249-90481	90481-95316	95316-100333	100333-105349	105349-124417	>124417
SISAMÓN	<15816	15816-23723	23723-28468	28468-30050	30050-31631	31631-33213	33213-39539	>39539
TERRER	<5023529	5023529-8608663	8608663-9237510	9237510-9544704	9544704-10047057	10047057-10549410	10549410-11485451	>11485451
TOBED	<75839	75839-118612	118612-137393	137393-144094	144094-151678	151678-159262	159262-184744	>184744
TORRALBA DE RIBOTA	<59056	59056-93192	93192-107139	107139-112207	112207-118112	118112-124018	124018-143032	>143032
TORREHERMOSA	<30633	30633-48518	48518-55607	55607-58203	58203-61266	61266-64329	64329-74014	>74014
TORRELAPAJA	<14229	14229-22522	22522-25826	25826-27034	27034-28457	28457-29880	29880-34393	>34393
TORRIJO DE LA CAÑADA	<97993	97993-155712	155712-177974	177974-186187	186187-195987	195987-205786	205786-236261	>236261
VALTORRES	<31636	31636-50147	50147-57435	57435-60109	60109-63273	63273-66436	66436-76398	>76398
VELILLA DE JILOCA	<32930	32930-51888	51888-59727	59727-62567	62567-65860	65860-69153	69153-79832	>79832
VILLAFELICHE	<66863	66863-106856	106856-121547	121547-127040	127040-133726	133726-140413	140413-160596	>160596
VILLALBA DE PEREJIL	<25827	25827-40373	40373-46786	46786-49072	49072-51654	51654-54237	54237-62935	>62935
VILALENGUA	<116992	116992-187161	187161-212708	212708-222285	222285-233984	233984-245684	245684-280808	>280808
VILLARROYA DE LA SIERRA	<178602	178602-280376	280376-323751	323751-339344	339344-357204	357204-375064	375064-434033	>434033
VILUEÑA, LA	<19088	19088-28632	28632-34359	34359-36268	36268-38176	38176-40085	40085-47721	>47721

2.2.6 Ad-hoc calculation for JALON participants

As mentioned in section 2.2.1, the values shown on the labels are not real values since they are an approximation with the census data. In order to make a calculation according to the real consumption it is optimal that participants can provide us with their real consumption data (preferably those corresponding to the year 2015 to calculate the thresholds of the label, or alternatively consumption of the year 2022). In this way, a real label can be established and the energy consumption of the people participating in the project can be analyzed correctly.

3. Socio-economic label: "Reverting depopulation"

The "Reverting Depopulation" label entails a classification designed to analyze the population figures of each municipality to assess trends over the years. Rural areas are experiencing depopulation as individuals are relocating to urban centers. One of our ambitious objectives is to reverse this trend and encourage people to return to rural communities. The mechanism we have created involves the use of a label, similar to previous ones, using census data to categorize each village into specific levels, with the aim of increasing the population figures to levels comparable to those of the 1990s.

Rural areas are characterized by a consistent decline in the number of inhabitants. This can be illustrated by the evolution of inhabitants in two different villages from the Calatayud region from 1995 to 2022, shown in Figure 1. The trend of such evolution is given by the least square regression, which linear model shows a negative slope, signifying that the number of residents recorded in the census has steadily decreased over the years 1996-2022. In this figure, two examples (Ateca and Munébrega) are illustrated that reflect the prevailing situation in the vast majority of the villages.

Figure 1. trends in depopulation of rural areas. Examples of two villages: Ateca (blue) and Munébrega (orange)

Nevertheless, three villages of the region (Calatayud, Paracuellos de Jiloca, and Sediles), have positive trends, as the population of these municipalities has increased. These positive slopes are shown in Figures 3, 4 and 5 for Calatayud, Paracuellos de Jiloca and Sediles, respectively.

Figure 2. Positive depopulation trend for the village of Calatayud

Figure 3. Positive slope in depopulation for the village of Paracuellos de Jiloca

Figure 4. Positive trend in depopulation for the village of Sediles

The methodology for developing this label is straightforward: we have obtained municipal census data for each town from 1996 to 2022 from the INE [6] and calculated the least square regression for each trend. It is evident that in most cases, the slopes are negative, confirming the rural exodus. Using this linear equation, we established different levels corresponding to the approximation for the years 1996 (A), 2000 (B), 2009 (C), 2015 (D), 2022 (E), and 2030 (F). The latter level is also calculated to determine the population size we would reach if the current trend continues, in an effort to motivate individuals to enhance these values.

On the other hand, the calculation for the three villages with a positive trend is different and is conducted as follows: we designate the current level (2022) on the label as C, and the higher levels are approximations of what is expected for 2030 and 2050. The lower levels correspond to previous years, unlike the other cases, for these three towns: 2050 (A), 2030 (B), 2022 (C), 2015 (D), 2009 (E), and 2000 (F).

In Table 13, you can observe the labels for each municipality, with an asterisk (*) denoting the three villages with a different calculation, as explained before.

Table 13. Reverting depopulation label (number of people)

Municipality	A	B	C	D	E	F	G
ABANTO	>193	193-176	176-138	138-112	112-82	82-48	<48
ALARBA	>168	168-162	162-147	147-138	138-127	127-114	<114

ALCONCHEL DE ARIZA	>170	170-152	152-112	112-85	85-54	54-18	<18
ALHAMA DE ARAGÓN	>1240	1240-1205	1205-1127	1127-1075	1075-1015	1015-946	<946
ANIÑÓN	>932	932-893	893-806	806-747	747-679	679-601	<601
ARÁNDIGA	>542	542-500	500-406	406-344	344-271	271-188	<188
ARIZA	>1393	1393-1346	1346-1240	1240-1170	1170-1088	1088-994	<994
ATECA	>2143	2143-2094	2094-1985	1985-1912	1912-1828	1828-1731	<1731
BELMONTE DE GRACIÁN	>296	296-278	278-238	238-212	212-181	181-146	<146
BERDEJO	>67	67-64	64-58	58-54	54-49	49-44	<44
BIJUESCA	>141	141-133	133-115	115-104	104-90	90-74	<74
BORDALBA	>109	109-100	100-79	79-64	64-48	48-29	<29
BUBIERCA	>111	111-103	103-85	85-73	73-59	59-43	<43
CABOLAFUENTE	>87	87-78	78-58	58-44	44-29	29-11	<11
CALATAYUD*	>24247	24247-22050	22050-21171	21171-20402	20402-19743	19743-18754	<18754
CALMARZA	>98	98-93	93-80	80-71	71-61	61-49	<49
CAMPILLO DE ARAGÓN	>199	199-188	188-164	164-149	149-130	130-109	<109
CARENAS	>241	241-230	230-205	205-188	188-169	169-147	<147
CASTEJÓN DE ALARBA	>119	119-113	113-100	100-90	90-80	80-68	<68
CASTEJÓN DE LAS ARMAS	>140	140-131	131-111	111-97	97-81	81-63	<63
CERVERA DE LA CAÑADA	>362	362-348	348-317	317-295	295-271	271-243	<243
CETINA	>768	768-740	740-677	677-635	635-586	586-530	<530
CIMBALLA	>161	161-151	151-126	126-110	110-91	91-69	<69
CLARÉS DE RIBOTA	>114	114-107	107-91	91-80	80-68	68-54	<54
CODOS	>299	299-285	285-253	253-231	231-206	206-177	<177
CONTAMINA	>60	60-55	55-44	44-37	37-29	29-19	<19
EMBID DE ARIZA	>81	81-73	73-57	57-46	46-33	33-19	<19
FRASNO, EL	>586	586-552	552-475	475-424	424-364	364-296	<296
FUENTES DE JILOCA	>370	370-345	345-288	288-250	250-205	205-155	<155
GODOJOS	>70	70-66	66-56	56-49	49-41	41-32	<32
IBDES	>605	605-571	571-494	494-443	443-384	384-315	<315
JARABA	>339	339-334	334-321	321-313	313-303	303-291	<291
MALANQUILLA	>142	142-135	135-120	120-109	109-97	97-83	<83
MALUENDA	>1061	1061-1050	1050-1023	1023-1005	1005-984	984-961	<961
MARA	>220	220-212	212-196	196-185	185-172	172-157	<157
MIEDES DE ARAGÓN	>532	532-515	515-478	478-453	453-423	423-390	<390
MONREAL DE ARIZA	>301	301-282	282-238	238-210	210-176	176-138	<138
MONTERDE	>262	262-244	244-205	205-178	178-147	147-112	<112
MONTÓN	>154	154-145	145-123	123-108	108-91	91-72	<72
MORATA DE JILOCA	>342	342-328	328-296	296-275	275-250	250-222	<222
MORÉS	>516	516-485	485-416	416-371	371-317	317-256	<256
MOROS	>573	573-535	535-448	448-391	391-324	324-247	<247
MUNÉBREGA	>493	493-476	476-436	436-410	410-379	379-344	<344
NIGÜELLA	>122	122-112	112-89	89-73	73-55	55-35	<35
NUÉVALOS	>355	355-350	350-337	337-328	328-319	319-307	<307
OLVÉS	>166	166-155	155-129	129-112	112-92	92-70	<70
ORERA	>136	136-134	134-127	127-123	123-118	118-112	<112
PARACUELLOS DE JILOCA*	>729	729-639	639-602	602-571	571-544	544-503	<503
PARACUELLOS DE LA RIBERA	>308	308-278	278-211	211-166	166-114	114-54	<54
POZUEL DE ARIZA	>25	25-24	23	22	21	1-19	<19
RUESCA	>92	92-89	89-81	81-76	76-70	70-63	<63
SABIÑÁN	>947	947-902	902-801	801-734	734-656	656-566	<566

SEDILES*	>108	108-106	106-105	104	103	102	<102
SISAMÓN	>83	83-74	74-53	53-40	40-24	24-6	<6
TERRER	>643	643-615	615-554	554-512	512-464	464-409	<409
TOBED	>286	286-275	275-249	249-232	232-213	213-190	<190
TORRALBA DE RIBOTA	>224	224-215	215-196	196-183	183-168	168-151	<151
TORREHERMOSA	<122	122-112	112-89	89-73	73-55	55-35	<35
TORRELAPAJA	>45	45-43	43-39	39-36	36-33	33-29	<29
TORRIJO DE LA CAÑADA	>419	419-382	382-299	299-243	243-179	179-104	<104
VALTORRES	>115	115-108	108-92	92-81	81-68	68-54	<54
VELILLA DE JILOCA	>126	126-120	120-107	107-99	99-89	89-77	<77
VILLAFELICHE	>252	252-237	237-205	205-183	183-157	157-129	<129
VILLALBA DE PEREJIL	>124	124-120	120-110	110-104	104-96	96-87	<87
VILLALENGUA	>455	455-431	431-377	377-342	342-300	300-252	<252
VILLARROYA DE LA SIERRA	>727	727-681	681-576	576-506	506-424	424-331	<331
VILUEÑA, LA	>115	115-111	111-100	100-93	93-84	84-75	<75

3.1. Social indicators to evaluate the impact of the energy community.

The evaluation of social impact is complex, especially concerning energy communities, community projects, bioenergy, and social farming. A literature review has revealed a range of social indicators crucial for analysing proposed scenarios. These projects influence both the community and individuals, highlighting the need for comprehensive assessment.

Table 14 presents identified indicators categorized into eight key impact areas within the community: employment, economic development, social acceptability, energy access, information and education, participation, societal development, and behavioural impacts. These categories can be further grouped into three main types of impacts:

1. Individual Wellbeing: Focuses on individual benefits, encompassing success, education, health, and welfare.
2. Community Wellbeing: Addresses the social dimensions affecting a particular community or region.
3. Societal Impacts: Relates to indicators beyond the community or region, addressing global-scale social challenges.

Refer to Table 14 for a detailed display of these indicators.

Table 14. Social indicators organized by the community level.

Impact	Level	Indicator	References
Employment	Community well-being	Job creation	[9] [10] [11] [12]
	Community well-being	Creation of new business	[9] [10] [11] [13]
	Individual well-being	Acquisition of job skills	[14] [9] [12]
	Community well-being	Employment in the sector	[10]
	Community well-being	Job creation in industry	[10]
	Community well-being	Job creation in rural areas	[10]
Economic development	Community well-being	Improvement of local infrastructure	[9] [10] [12]
	Community well-being	Community investment	[11] [10] [11] [13] [12]
	Community well-being	Local economic development	[9] [10] [11] [13]
	Community well-being	Direct economic impacts	[9]
	Community well-being	Indirect economic impacts	[13]
	Community well-being	Economic feasibility	[10]
	Societal impacts	GDP increase	[10] [12]
	Societal impacts	Sector contribution to GDP	[10] [12]
Social acceptability	Community well-being	Contribution to technology development	[10] [12]
	Societal impacts	Local community engagement	[9]
	Societal impacts	Public opinion	[9] [12]
Energy access	Societal impacts	Social acceptability	[10] [12]
	Individual well-being	Households with access to electricity grid	[10]
	Societal impacts	Energy security	[9] [13]
	Societal impacts	Electricity costs reduction	[14] [11] [13] [12]
	Societal impacts	Energy access	[10] [12]
	Individual well-being	Consumption of self-generation energy	[13] [12]
	Individual well-being	Training or educational provided to employees	[9] [10]

Information and education	Individual well-being	Developing technical skills	[9] [10]
	Individual well-being	Training and educational programs: long-life learning	[9] [10]
	Individual well-being	Access to information and knowledge	[10] [11] [12]
Participation	Societal impacts	Improve social relationship	[12]
	Community well-being	Effective stakeholder participation	[10]
	Community well-being	Communication with local authorities	[12]
	Community well-being	Community participation	[13] [10] [11] [13] [12]
	Community well-being	Community involved in decision making	[10] [11]
Society development	Societal impacts	Poverty reduction	[10] [11] [13]
	Societal impacts	Improvement in life quality	[14] [10]
	Societal impacts	Reduce social isolation	[14] [11]
	Community well-being	Build local capacity	[12]
Behavioural impacts	Individual well-being	Energy consumption reduction	[11] [12]
	Community well-being	Reduction of fossil fuels imports	[10]
	Individual well-being	Developing behavioural skills	[9]
	Individual well-being	Actions and efforts to be more responsible toward environmental issues	[11]
	Individual well-being	Change in citizens behaviour: raise awareness on climate change	[11] [12]
	Individual well-being	Household behavioural change measures	[12]

In this regard, the indicators have been ranked on a scale (refer to Table 15), as previously mentioned. At the bottom of the scale, it can be found indicators with less community impact and more focused on individual aspects. As you move up the scale, the indicators demonstrate increasing collective benefits.

This scaled system aims to measure the socioeconomic impact of the Energy Community (EC) through a step-by-step evaluation. By analysing the EC's progress using these indicators, we can understand how it evolves. Advancing technically and economically as it reaches certain levels, the EC achieves greater social impact at each step of the scale. Consequently, this approach allows us to determine the socioeconomic status of the EC based on these indicators, which at the end must be related to the original idea of JALON inhabitants of reverting depopulation.

Table 15 provides the proposed methods for measuring these indicators, denoted by '#' indicating the 'number of'.

Table 15. Scaled system according to the indicators to evaluate the social aspects of the EC.

LABEL	Social indicator	Measurement methodology	Units
		+collective benefits	
Local capacity building	Local community engagement	Survey: are there more people in the region?	%
	Public opinion	Survey: are there more people in the community?	%
	Social acceptability	Survey: comparison of the levels of acceptance of the project before and at present to evaluate the perception of the community.	%
	Improvement in life quality	Access to basic services for each village: energy, water, health and education.	#
	GDP increase	Local business growth: increase in revenues	€
	Local economic development	Increased investment in the region	€

Improvement of local economy	Direct economic impacts	Savings for community members	€
	Creation of new business	Number of new businesses created	#
	Improve social relationship	Survey: collaboration and positive interactions in the community	%
	Improvement of local infrastructure	Investments in local infrastructure	€
Changes in community's behaviours	Energy consumption reduction	Percentage of users that reduce their energy consumption at home: labelling system	%
	Long-life learning	Number of training activities for people interested	#
	Community involved in decision making	Percentage of community members involved in the decision-making process	%
	Indirect economic impacts	Savings for municipalities by photovoltaic installations	€
Energy security and access	Reduction of fossil fuels imports	Increase in the number of renewable energy facilities	Δ%
	Energy access	Percentage of household with energy access	%
	Poverty reduction	Percentage of poverty reduction	Δ%
	Electricity costs reduction	Money paid per capita for electricity	€
	Households with access to electricity grid	Number of households	#
	Consumption of self-generation energy	Number of prosumers	#
Employment	Contribution to technology development	Adoption of technology innovation: renewable energy facilities, energy efficiency systems...	#
	Acquisition of job skills	Number of workshops with professionals	#
	Job creation	Number of new jobs in PV sector, rural areas and industry	#
Participation	Communication with local authorities	Percentage of municipalities contacted	%
	Community investment	Money invested by the EC members	€
	Community participation	Percentage of inhabitants participating in the EC	%
	Access to information and knowledge	Number of events to inform about the EC	#
+individual benefits/-collective impact			

The purpose of this label is to scale, step by step, from the more individual benefits to a more collective society (from the bottom). As each village is different, no value can be established for the moment for the different levels of the scale.

4. Future use of the labels

The use of these labels will be as follows: once the photovoltaic installations are in operation, we will evaluate the energy consumption data provided by Datadis for the different municipalities of the region, this will give us the energy consumption from the grid. On the other hand, we will evaluate the consumptions of the photovoltaic installations of the region for each municipality and, in this way, adding both energy consumptions we will know the consumption of the municipalities. With this information, we will know if they have achieved a reduction in energy consumption or an increase compared to those on the label.

However, it is necessary to evaluate specifically the different scenarios that we can find, since we do not only have options for behavioural changes.

Among these future scenarios we find:

- Scenario 1: Reduction of consumption. This may be due to villagers leaving the villages.
- Scenario 2: Reduction of consumption. Due to behavioural changes in individuals who are part of the energy community.
- Scenario 3: Increase in consumption. May be due to new people coming to live in the villages.
- Scenario 4: Increase in consumption. It may be due to people electrifying consumption that was not electric before (heating, car...).

This specific evaluation will need to take into account factors already considered in table 16 together with some official data coming from the Statistical National Offices.

As for getting the necessary information to establish the “reverting depopulation” label, we will create the specific tools necessary to monitor the different indicators.

In addition, to calculate emissions, it will be necessary to know the energy source, as discussed throughout the report. In the case of photovoltaic installations, an emission factor must also be taken into account and the following equations (3) and (4) must be used to calculate the emissions produced by PV:

$$\text{Carbon footprint}_{\text{energy prod}} = \text{Carbon footprint}_{\text{others energy prod}} - \text{Carbon footprint}_{\text{PV energy prod}} \quad (3)$$

$$\text{Carbon footprint}_{\text{PV energy prod}} = \text{Energy produced}_{\text{PV}} \cdot \text{EF}_{\text{PV energy prod}} \quad (4)$$

Table 16 Carbon emission intensity of electricity generation

Carbon emission intensity for electricity generation	
Energy production EF (kg CO ₂ /kWh)	0.190
Photovoltaic electricity production EF (kg CO ₂ /kWh)	0.0305

5. References

- [1] A. B. Cristóbal, C. Sanz-Cuadrado, Z. Zhang, P. Radhan y M. Victoria, «D1.1 - Near Zero-Emissions Citizens Label - AURORA Project,» 2022.
- [2] European Commission, «Commission Staff Working Document SWD/2020/176: Impact Assessment on Stepping up Europe's 2030 climate ambition Investing in a climate-neutral future for the benefit of our people,» Brussels, 2020.
- [3] «DATADIS,» [En línea]. Available: <https://datadis.es/queries>. [Último acceso: 26 07 2023].
- [4] «Our World in Data - energy use per person,» [En línea]. Available: https://ourworldindata.org/grapher/per-capita-energy-use?tab=chart&time=2015..latest&country=~OWID_EU27. [Último acceso: 26 07 2023].
- [5] L. Mantzos, T. Wiesenthal, N. Matei, S. Tchung-Ming, M. Rózsai y H. Russ, «JRC-IDEES Integrated Database of the European Energy Sector,» 2017.
- [6] Instituto Nacional de Estadística, «Cifras oficiales de población de los municipios españoles en aplicación de la Ley de Bases del Régimen Local (Art. 17),» INE, 1 1 2022. [En línea]. Available: <https://www.ine.es/jaxiT3/Tabla.htm?t=2907&L=0>. [Último acceso: 20 10 2023].
- [7] B. Koffi, A. Cerutti y A. Kona, «CoM Default Emission Factors for the Member States of the European Union [Internet]. Available from:,» 2017.
- [8] M. de los Llanos Matea y A. Muñoz-Julve, «El gasto energético de las empresas españolas industriales y de servicios,» 2022.
- [9] E. Fedorova y E. pongrácz, «Cumulative social effect assessment framework to evaluate the accumulation of social sustainability benefits of regional bioenergy value chains,» *Renewable energy*, vol. 131, pp. 1073-1088, 2019.
- [10] M. L. Brinkman, B. Wicke, A. P. Faaij y F. van der Hilst, «Projecting socio-economic impacts of bioenergy: Current status and limitations of ex-ante quantification methods,» *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews*, vol. 15, 2019.
- [11] Heinrich Böll Foundation Greece, ELECTRA Energy Cooperative y REScoop, «The social impact of energy communities in Greece».
- [12] A. L. Berka y E. Creamer, «Taking stock of the local impacts of community owned renewable energy: A review and research agenda,» *Renewable and Sustainability Energy Reviews*, vol. 82, pp. 3400-3419, 2018.
- [13] S. Adams, D. Brown, J. P. Cárdenas Álvarez, R. Chitchyan, M. J. Fell, U. J. Hahnel, K. Hojckova, C. Johnson, L. Klein, M. Montakhabi, K. Say, A. Singh y N. Watson, «Social and Economic Value in Emerging Decentralized Energy Business Models: A Critical Review,» *Energies*, vol. 14, 2021.
- [14] F. Basset, «The Evaluation of Social Farming through Social Return on Investment: A Review,» *Sustainability*, vol. 15, 2023.

- [15] B. Koffi, A. K. Cerutti, M. Duer, A. Iancu, ,. A. Kona y G. Janssens-Maenhout, «Covenant of Mayors for Climate and Energy: Default emission factors for local emission inventories - Version 2017,» 2017.
- [16] «Carbon intensity of electricity per kWh, 2000 to 2020,» Our World in Data, [En línea]. Available: <https://ourworldindata.org/grapher/carbon-intensity-electricity?tab=chart>. [Último acceso: March 2022].
- [17] IPCC, «IPCC Guidelines for National Greenhouse Gas Inventories. Vol.1 General Guidance and Reporting. Chapter 1. Introduction to the 2006 guidelines,» 2006.
- [18] G. Fontaras, N. Zacharof y B. Ciuffo, «Fuel consumption and CO2 emissions from passenger cars in Europe – Laboratory versus real-world emissions,» *Progress in Energy and Combustion Science*, vol. 60, pp. 97-131, 2017.
- [19] L. Ntziachristos y Z. Samaras, «EMEP/EEA air pollutant emission inventory guidebook 2019 (1.A.3.b.i, 1.A.3.b.ii, 1.A.3.b.iii, 1.A.3.b.iv Passenger cars, light commercial trucks, heavy-duty vehicles including buses and motor cycles),» 2021.
- [20] «Fuel types of new buses: electric 10.6%, alternative fuels 10.5%, hybrid 10.1%, diesel 68.8% share un 2021,» ACEA driving mobility for Europe, 15 03 2022. [En línea]. Available: <https://www.acea.auto/fuel-cv/fuel-types-of-new-buses-electric-10-6-alternative-fuels-10-5-hybrid-10-1-diesel-68-8-share-in-2021>. [Último acceso: 30 05 2022].
- [21] M. Weiss, E. Helmers y K. Cloos, «Energy efficiency trade-offs in small to large electric vehicles,» *Environmental Sciences Europe*, pp. 32-46, 2020.
- [22] IPCC, «IPCC Guidelines for National Greenhouse Inventories. Volumen 2: Energy. Chapter 2: Stationary Combustion,» 2006.
- [23] «Converting Fuel to kWh and CO2e,» [En línea]. Available: <https://travelifestaybetter.com/wp-content/uploads/2019/02/17-Fuel-Conversion-Rates-to-kWh-and-CO2e.pdf>.
- [24] C. Sanz-Cuadrado, A. B. Cristóbal, Z. Zhang, P. Radhan y M. Victoria, «D1.1 - Near Zero-Emissions Citizens Label - AURORA Project,» 2022.
- [25] Instituto Nacional de Estadística (INE), «Cifras oficiales del padrón por municipio,» 01 01 2023.

APPENDIX

Three different labels have been defined for the citizen's category: electricity, heating and transport. Electricity and heating consumption refer to household energy consumption and transport, to the daily passenger mobility. The choice of these three sectors is to change daily habits related directly to energy consumption: reducing the electricity at home or going to work by bus instead of driving your car alone. In this section, we will explain how to calculate the energy consumption and emissions to be more aware about energy habits and change daily energy behaviours.

1. Definition of the different categories for the label

The average calculation is based on the annual energy consumption for 2015 and the emissions associated are calculated and shown in Tables A1, A2 and A3. The carbon footprint is calculated by multiplying the energy consumption by an emission factor (EF) of the energy source: for the electricity is used the EF of the national grid [15] [16] and for the heating is needed the EF of the heating fuel (in this case, natural gas is the most common heating fuel in the country) [15]. The transport's calculation is different. It considers the total amount of energy consumption in the country and is divided by the number of inhabitants. The emissions' calculation follows the same procedure [5].

Table A1 Carbon footprint of domestic electricity consumption per capita (2015 data)

Electricity consumption and emissions	
a. Domestic electricity consumption per capita (kWh)	1,607.22
b. National electricity emission factor (kg CO ₂ /kWh)	0.307
c. Electricity consumption carbon footprint (a*b) (kg CO ₂)	493.42

Table A2 Domestic thermal energy consumption carbon footprint per capita (2015 data)

Thermal consumption and emissions	
a. Domestic thermal energy consumption per capita (kWh)	2,168.76
b. Natural gas emission factor (kg CO ₂ /kWh)	0.202
c. Thermal energy consumption carbon footprint (a*b) (kg CO ₂)	438.09

Table A3 Energy consumption and CO₂ emissions for passenger transport (2015 data)

Transport energy consumption and emissions	
Total energy consumption (MWh)	2.80E+08
Total CO ₂ emissions (t CO ₂)	6.98E+07
Number of inhabitants	46,449,565
Energy consumption per capita (kWh/capita)	6,023
CO ₂ emissions per capita (kg CO ₂ /capita)	1,502

Table A4 shows the different categories using the data shown in Tables A1, A2 and A3 and the percentages to calculate the different levels, shown in Table 1.

Table A4 Definition of annual values for the labelling system

Level	Electricity consumption		Heating consumption		Mobility		TOTAL	
	Energy demand (kWh)	Footprint (kg CO ₂)	Energy demand (kWh)	Footprint (kg CO ₂)	Energy demand (kWh)	Footprint (kg CO ₂)	Energy demand (kWh)	Footprint (kg CO ₂)
A+	<804	<247	<1084	<219	<3011	<751	<4899	<1266
A	804-1205	247-370	1084-1627	219-329	3011-5059	751-1262	4899-7891	1266-1974
B	1205-1447	370-444	1627-1952	329-394	5059-5481	1262-1367	7891-8879	1974-2221
C	1447-1527	444-469	1952-2060	394-416	5481-5721	1367-1427	8879-9303	2221-2329
D	1527-1607	469-493	2060-2169	416-438	5721-6023	1427-1502	9303-9799	2329-2451
E	1607-1688	493-518	2169-2277	438-460	6023-6324	1502-1577	9799-10289	2451-2574
F	1688-2009	518-617	2277-2711	460-548	6324-6986	1577-1743	10289-11706	2574-2929
G	>2009	>617	>2711	>548	>6986	>1743	>11706	>2929

2. Definition of the equations to calculate the labels

The calculation for the current use of energy follows the equations explained in this section. As mentioned before, the three categories considered for the label are electricity and heating at the household level and passenger transport. The IPCC [17] defines the carbon footprint as a measurement tool used to quantify greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions generated during a specific activity. These emissions, associated with energy consumption, can be calculated using equation (5). The activity data represents the source of the emissions, such as fuel combustion or electricity usage, while EF denotes the emission factor associated with that particular activity.

$$\text{Carbon footprint (t CO}_2\text{)} = \text{activity data} \cdot \text{EF}_{\text{activity}} \quad (5)$$

Carbon footprint calculation for the electricity consumption

The carbon footprint resulting from electricity consumption can be calculated using equation (6). In this equation, the input data includes the household's electricity consumption (kWh), the number of individuals residing in the house, and the period over which the consumption is measured (days, months, etc.). The EF represents the emission factor specific to the national grid (kg CO₂/kWh).

$$\text{Carbon Footprint}_{\text{electricity consumption}} = \frac{\text{electricity consumption}}{\text{capita}} \cdot \text{EF}_{\text{electricity consumption}} \quad (6)$$

The carbon footprint of the electricity produced by photovoltaic (PV) facilities owned by citizens, industries or other entities is deducted from the total carbon footprint. This deduction is explained in Section 4.

Carbon footprint calculation for the thermal energy consumption

To calculate the carbon footprint related to thermal consumption, equation (7) is used. The input data required for the calculation includes the household's thermal consumption (kWh), the number of individuals residing in the dwelling, the type of heating fuel utilized, and the period over which the consumption is monitored (days, months, etc.). The EFs [7] associated with various heating fuels for households can be found in Table A5. In

instances where renewable sources or technologies are used for heating systems [15] [18], the corresponding emission factors (EFs) are provided in Table A6. For electric heating systems, the calculation is based on electricity consumption (while considering that the electricity consumption may increase, the overall household energy consumption will not be overestimated). In this case, the heating component should be left empty, and it is necessary to select the electric heating system from the thermal inputs.

$$\text{Carbon footprint}_{\text{thermal energy}} = \text{heating thermal consumption} / \text{capita} \cdot \text{EF}_{\text{fuel}} \quad (7)$$

Table A5 Heating fuels emission factors.

Fuel	Emission Factor (kg CO ₂ /kWh)
Heating oil	0.267
Natural gas	0.202
LPG (liquefied petrol gas)	0.227

Table A6 Heating renewable energy sources emission factors.

Renewable energy source	Emission Factor (kg CO ₂ /kWh)
Biomass	0.118
Locally-produced biomass	0.000
Geothermal	0.050
Solar thermal	0.040
District heating	0.268

Carbon footprint calculation for transport energy consumption

The calculation of passenger transport energy consumption and emissions follows a different approach since it is more complicated than the procedures explained before. The inputs required for this calculation include the type of vehicle used (public or private), the energy source utilized by the vehicle (fuel, electricity), and the distance travelled, as depicted in equation (8) [19]. We calculated the energy consumption and emissions per capita based on vehicle occupancy (see Table A7). Users only need to input the vehicle used and the distance travelled, and the energy use and its emissions are calculated with this data.

$$\text{Carbon footprint}_{\text{transport}} = \text{EF}_{\text{vehicle}} \cdot \text{Traveled distance} \quad (8)$$

Table A7 Energy consumption and emission factor per passenger and kilometre

Type of vehicle	Vehicle consumption per passenger according to vehicle occupancy					Units	Emission factor per passenger according to vehicle occupancy					Units
	1	2	3	4	5		1	2	3	4	5	
Fuel car	0.748	0.390	0.271	0.211	0.175	kWh/p-km	0.1897	0.0771	0.0557	0.0451	0.0388	kg CO ₂ /p-km
Electric car	0.327	0.166	0.113	0.086	0.070		0.0621	0.0107	0.0075	0.0059	0.0049	
Plug-in hybrid electric car	0.383	0.200	0.139	0.108	0.090		0.0849	0.0170	0.0118	0.0092	0.0077	
Motorcycles and mopeds	0.439	0.235	-	-	-		0.1112	0.0280	-	-	-	
Electric motorcycle	0.132	0.066	-	-	-		0.0251	0.0018	-	-	-	
Electric bike	0.012	-	-	-	-		0.0023	-	-	-	-	
Electric scooter	0.026	-	-	-	-		0.0049	-	-	-	-	
-	Almost empty	Average		Nearly full		-	Almost empty	Average		Nearly full		-
Urban bus (by default)	0.8056	0.2562	0.1523	kWh/p-km	0.1918	0.0610	0.0363	kg CO ₂ /p-km				
Electric bus					0.1531	0.0487	0.0289					
Hybrid-electric bus					0.1801	0.0573	0.03421					
Diesel bus					0.2071	0.0659	0.0392					
Alternative fuels bus					0.1837	0.0585	0.0347					
Subway, tram and urban light rails	0.2243	0.0713	0.0424	kWh/p-km	0.0427	0.0136	0.0081	kg CO ₂ /p-km				
Electric passenger trains	0.9026	0.2870	0.1707		0.1715	0.0545	0.0324					
Diesel passenger trains	1.3302	0.4230	0.2515		0.3546	0.1128	0.0670					
High-speed trains	0.2868	0.0912	0.0542		0.0545	0.0173	0.0103					
Plane	369			kWh/p	95.437			kg CO ₂ /p				

The different types of buses can be found in Table A8 (data from [7] [5] [16] [20]) and the energy consumption and emissions per capita for aviation are shown in Table A9 [5]. It is important to note that all the calculations in this study are simple because we do not want to have an accurate carbon footprint but to increase awareness of citizens and users to reduce their consumption and emission in these three sectors.

Table A8 Emissions Factor for the different urban bus choices

Type of bus	Emission Factor (kg CO ₂ /kWh)
Default bus	0.238
Electric bus	0.190
Hybrid-electric bus	0.224
Alternative fuels bus	0.228
Diesel bus	0.257

Table A9 Energy consumption and emissions for aviation per flight per capita

Energy consumption and emissions - aviation	
Consumption per flight per capita (kWh/ passenger)	369.0
Emissions per flight and per capita (kg CO ₂ /passenger)	95.4

Overall carbon footprint

The final carbon footprint is calculated following equation (9) where all carbon footprints (CF) explained previously are considered. The deduction of the energy produced is explained in Section 4, as mentioned before.

$$\text{Carbon footprint}_{\text{overall}} = \text{CF}_{\text{elect cons}} + \text{CF}_{\text{heating cons}} + \text{CF}_{\text{transport cons}} - \text{CF}_{\text{energy prod}} \quad (9)$$